

Sites of *O*-alkylation and *O*-glycosylation in naturally occurring phenolics using Kalidhar shifts

Meera

Department of Chemistry, KM Government College, Narwana, Jind-126 102, Haryana, India

Manuscript received 14 November 2007, revised 17 October 2008, accepted 31 March 2009

Abstract : Kalidhar shifts which involve comparison of ^1H NMRs of peracetates have been shown to be useful in locating the sites of *O*-alkylation and *O*-glycosylation in naturally occurring phenolics.

Keywords : *O*-Alkylation, Kalidhar shift, *O*-glycosylation, phenolics.

Introduction

^1H NMR shifts have been shown to be helpful in locating the site of *O*-alkylation and *O*-glycosylation in naturally occurring phenolics. A comparison of ^1H NMR spectra of the peracetates of hydroxyaromatic with that of methoxyaromatic shows that protons *para* to the site of difference undergoes a larger change in chemical shift (Δ). In absence of a *para* proton, *ortho* proton/s undergoes/undergo larger change/s in chemical shifts. In flavones, 3-*O*-alkylation shifts have been found to have a typical trend i.e. H-2' and H-6' undergo negative and numerically larger changes in chemical shifts. *O*-Alkylation and *O*-glycosylation shifts have been found to have similar trends.

Alkylation shifts for an aromatic proton (ΔH) are calculated from the difference of δ values of the proton in hydroxyaromatic peracetate to that of the corresponding proton in alkoxyaromatic peracetate.

Glycosylation shifts for an aromatic proton (ΔH) are calculated from the difference of δ values of the proton in hydroxyaromatic peracetate to that of the corresponding proton in aromatic *O*-glycoside peracetate.

Flavones

The ^1H NMR for aromatic protons (δ , CDCl_3) of 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone peracetate (1)¹ and 3,5-dihydroxy-7,8,4'-trimethoxyflavone peracetate (2)¹ have been shown in the structures. Alkylation shifts from 1 and 2 show that there are larger ΔH -3' and ΔH -5' and these are 4'-*O*-methylation shifts. Structures 1 and 2

differ at C-4' and H-3' and H-4' both of which are *ortho* to the site of difference C-4' and have undergone larger changes in chemical shifts.

1

2

Kalidhar shifts for 4'-*O*-methylation

$$1-2 : \Delta\text{H}-6 = 0, \Delta\text{H}-2',6' = 0.02, \Delta\text{H}-3',5' = 0.24$$

(δ Values of 2 have been subtracted from the corresponding δ values of 1)

The chemical shifts for the aromatic protons (δ , CDCl_3) of 3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone peracetate (3)² and 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavone 3-*O*-(*p*-coumaryl)glucoside peracetate (4)³ are shown along with the structures. The 3-*O*-glycosylation shifts from 3 minus 4 have been placed below the structures. There are negative and larger ΔH -2' and ΔH -6' which have been observed as a typical trend for 3-*O*-glycosylation shifts.

3

7

4

Kalidhar shifts for 3-*O*-glycosylation

$$3-4 : \Delta H-6 = -0.02, \Delta H-8 = -0.07, \Delta H-2',6' = -0.26, \\ \Delta H-3' = -0.07$$

The 3-*O*-methylation shifts are similar to 3-*O*-glycosylation shifts becomes evident from 5^2 and 6^4 data shown along with structures.

5

6

Kalidhar shifts for 3-*O*-methylation

$$5-6 : \Delta H-6 = 0.04, \Delta H-8 = -0.03, \Delta H-2',6' = -0.25, \Delta H-5' = 0.02$$

The alkylation shifts from 7^5 and 8^5 show that $\Delta H-8$ is larger. This is 5-*O*-methylation shift. Structures 7 and 8 differ at C-5. H-8 is *para* to the site of difference. More details of these shifts in flavones are available in literature⁶.

8

Kalidhar shifts for 5-*O*-methylation

$$7-8 : \Delta H-8 = 0.21, \Delta H-3' = 0.10, \Delta H-6' = 0.12$$

Isoflavones

The *O*-alkylation shifts from 5-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-2'',2''-dimethylpyrano(5'',6'':6,7)isoflavone peracetate (9)⁷ and 5,4'-dimethoxy-2'',2''-dimethylpyrano(5'',6'':6,7)isoflavone (10)⁷ show that $\Delta H-8$ is larger. More details on isoflavones⁸ for ΔH are available in literature.

9

10

Kalidhar shifts for 5-*O*-methylation

$$9-10 : \Delta H-2 = 0.10, \Delta H-8 = 0.23, \Delta H-2',6' = 0.08, \\ \Delta H-3',5' = 0.09$$

Coumarins

The alkylation shifts from 7-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxycoumarin peracetate (11)⁹ and 5,6,7-trimethoxycoumarin (12)⁹ show that $\Delta H-8$ is larger.

Meera : Sites of *O*-alkylation and *O*-glycosylation in naturally occurring phenolics using Kalidhar shifts

Kalidhar shifts for 7-*O*-methylation

$$11-12 : \Delta H-3 = 0.11, \Delta H-4 = 0.03, \Delta H-8 = 0.24$$

Details on coumarins regarding these shifts are there in literature¹⁰.

Anthraquinones

6-*O*-Methylation shifts from 1,2,6,8-tetrahydroxy-3-methylantraquinone peracetate (13)¹¹ and 1,2,8-trihydroxy-6-methoxy-3-methylantraquinone peracetate (14)¹² show larger $\Delta H-5$ and $\Delta H-7$. Several anthraquinones¹³ have already been dealt with in this regard.

Kalidhar shifts for 6-*O*-methylation

$$13-14 : \Delta H-4 = 0.16, \Delta H-5 = 0.45, \Delta H-7 = 0.44$$

Xanthenes

8-*O*-Methylation shifts from 8-hydroxy-1,2,6-trimethoxyxanthone peracetate (15)¹⁴ and 1,2,6,8-tetramethoxyxanthone (16)¹⁴ show larger $\Delta H-5$ than $\Delta H-7$. Such shifts on xanthenes¹⁵ are available in literature.

Kalidhar shifts for 8-*O*-methylation

$$15-16 : \Delta H-3 = 0.02, \Delta H-4 = 0.01, \Delta H-5 = 0.39$$

Structural revision of an anthraquinone glycoside

Based upon Kalidhar shifts from emodin peracetate (17)¹⁶ and its *O*-glycoside peracetate (18), the structure of the glycoside has been shown to be emodin-8-*O*-rhamnosyl(1-2)glucoside¹⁶. Lin *et al.* had previously suggested the structure to be emodin-1-*O*-rhamnosyl(1-2)glucoside (19) which had been isolated from *Rhamnus formosana*¹⁷.

Kalidhar shifts for 8-*O*-glycosylation

$$17-18 : \Delta H-2 = 0.09, \Delta H-4 = 0.13, \Delta H-5 = 0.26, \Delta H-7 = 0.10$$

Structural revision of a flavone glycoside

Kalidhar shifts from 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavone peracetate (20)¹⁸ and 3,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavone 5-*O*-glucoside peracetate (21)¹⁸ show a larger $\Delta H-8$. The previously proposed structure for the glycoside is 5,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavone 3-*O*-rhamnoside (22)¹⁹. It has been revised to 3,4'-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethoxyflavone 5-*O*-rhamnoside (23)¹⁸ on the basis of these shifts.

21
Kalidhar shifts for 5-O-glycosylation

20-21 : $\Delta H-8 = 0.39$, $\Delta H-2',6' = 0.07$, $\Delta H-3',5' = 0.08$

5-O-Glycosylation and 7-O-glycosylation shifts in flavones have similar trends ($\Delta H-8 > \Delta H-6$) :

7-O-Glycosylation shifts from 24²⁰ and 25²¹ make it clear that $\Delta H-8 > \Delta H-6$. 5-O-Methylation shifts from 26⁵ and 27⁵ have similar trends. It is therefore essential to make interpretations consistent with $AlCl_3$ shifts in UV-Visible.

24

25

Kalidhar shifts for 7-O-glycosylation

24-25 : $\Delta H-3 = 0.01$, $\Delta H-6 = 0.19$, $\Delta H-8 = 0.24$,
 $\Delta H-2',6' = 0.03$, $\Delta H-3',5' = -0.04$

26

27

Kalidhar shifts for 5-O-methylation

26-27 : $\Delta H-6 = 0.22$, $\Delta H-8 = 0.30$, $\Delta H-3' = -0.03$, $\Delta H-5' = 0.00$

Extension of the shifts in one of the rings :

It is possible to calculate alkylation shifts for $\Delta H-5$ and $\Delta H-7$ from 17¹⁶ and 28²² despite the fact that alkylation shifts cannot be calculated for $\Delta H-2$ and $\Delta H-4$.

17

28

Kalidhar shifts for 8-O-methylation

17-28 : $\Delta H-5 = 0.61$, $\Delta H-7 = 0.39$

It looks pertinent to mention it here that chemical shifts for H-4 and H-5 in 28 have been interchanged in consultation with the existing literature data. In the original paper, $\delta 7.37$ and $\delta 7.63$ have been assigned for H-4 and H-5 respectively.

Solvent

It looks pertinent to mention it here that peracetates are soluble in $CDCl_3$, which is the solvent for the 1H NMR of the aforesaid compounds.

Usefulness of the shifts in locating site of methylation in kaempferol :

If 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxyflavone (kaempferol) has been isolated as its monomethyl ether derivative from a natural source then peracetate of the isolated compound is prepared with acetic anhydride and pyridine. Its 1H NMR spectrum is compared with that of kaempferol tetraacetate for the determination of position of Me in the natural sample. If O-Me is present at C-4', $\Delta H-3'$ and $\Delta H-5'$ will be larger. If O-methyl is present at C-3', $\Delta H-2'$ and $\Delta H-6'$ will be negative and numerically larger; if O-Me is present at C-5, $\Delta H-8$ will be larger; if O-Me is present at C-6, $\Delta H-6$ and $\Delta H-8$ will be larger. The shifts will help in making a distinction amongst 3-O-methylkaempferol, 5-O-methylkaempferol, 7-O-methylkaempferol and 4'-O-methylkaempferol. There could be problems in making a

clear-cut distinction between 5-*O*-methylflavone and 7-*O*-methylflavone. AlCl_3 shifts in UV-Visible are to be taken into consideration to arrive at the final conclusion.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. M. R. Parthasarthy, Retd. Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Delhi University, for his valuable suggestions in preparing this manuscript.

References

1. T. Horie, M. Tsukayama, Y. Kawamura and S. Yamamoto, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 1491.
2. Hemlata, MSc Thesis, 1988, Chemistry Department, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, India.
3. R. Higuchi and D. M. X. Donnelly, *Phytochemistry*, 1978, **17**, 787.
4. H. Guinaudeau, O. Seligmann, H. Wagner and A. Neszmelyi, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, **21**, 1113.
5. R. B. Filho and O. R. Gottlieb, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, **10**, 2433.
6. S. B. Kalidhar, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1989, 311; *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 2416.
7. E. M. Illivares, W. Lwandle, F. D. Monache and G. B. M. Bettola, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, **20**, 1763.
8. S. B. Kalidhar, *Proc. Indian Natl. Sci. Acad.*, 1990, **56A**, 217.
9. H. Wagner and S. Bladt, *Phytochemistry*, 1975, **14**, 2061.
10. S. B. Kalidhar, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1990, **102**, 737.
11. S. Kitanaka, F. Kimura and M. Takido, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1985, **33**, 1274.
12. S. B. Kalidhar and P. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 411.
13. S. B. Kalidhar, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 3459.
14. P. Rivalle, J. Massicot, M. Guyot and V. Plouvier, *Phytochemistry*, 1969, **8**, 1533.
15. S. B. Kalidhar, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1990, **70**, 525.
16. S. B. Kalidhar, *Phytochemistry*, 1992, **31**, 2905.
17. C. N. Lin, M. I. Chung, K. H. Ganand and C. M. Lu, *Phytochemistry*, 1991, **30**, 3103.
18. S. B. Kalidhar, *J. Natural Products*, 1990, **53**, 1565.
19. P. K. Jauhar, S. C. Sharma, J. S. Tandon and M. M. Dhar, *Phytochemistry*, 1979, **18**, 359.
20. M. Okigawa, N. U. Khan, N. Kawano and W. Rahman, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1975, 1563.
21. M. Ilyas, M. Perveen and S. M. Ahmad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 497.
22. A. Gupta, J. Singh and J. P. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 289.